

COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy 2021

TRANSLATING INNOVATIONS IN TESTING

SUMMARY REPORT

Contents

Executive Summary.....	3
Purpose of the Evidence Academy	5
Attendee Demographics/Characteristics	6
Summary of Keynote Presentations.....	8
Definitions and Summaries of Six Cross-Cutting Themes.....	15
Summary of Session Themes	16
Insights and Recommendations from Session Themes	17
Lessons Learned	24
Appendix	
◦ Acknowledgments.....	26
◦ COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy 2021 Agenda At-A-Glance.....	28

Executive Summary

Across the nation, diverse communities are rising to the challenges posed by the disproportionate impact of COVID-19. The inaugural **COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy 2021: Translating Innovations in Testing** brought together 319 researchers and community and governmental leaders to share their experiences, ideas, and recommendations to overcome disparities in COVID-19 testing. At the time of the event, national attention focused on the unprecedented logistics of rolling out access to COVID-19 vaccines. But testing for COVID-19 will remain a critical tool in the fight against the disease along with other mitigation strategies such as social distancing and use of masks.

This event was co-hosted by the National Institutes of Health (NIH)-funded Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics-Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) and the Community Engagement Alliance (CEAL) initiatives. RADx-UP is a network of 70+ currently funded projects across the United States. CEAL is comprised of 11 research teams working in 11 different states. Funded projects in RADx-UP and CEAL combined extends over five different racial and ethnic populations, over eight different types of health-related factors, and includes partnerships with academic institutions, community organizations, faith-based organizations, public health agencies, and other nonprofit organizations.

The two-day event, held February 24–25, 2021, focused on six, main, cross-cutting themes in COVID-19 testing:

 THEME 1
Cultural and Ethical Considerations

 THEME 4
Trustworthiness and Equity

 THEME 2
Social and Economic Costs

 THEME 5
Communication and Messaging

 THEME 3
Robust Data Science

 THEME 6
Contact Tracing and Case Investigation

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

On the first day of the event, keynote speakers addressed these themes. Before the event, attendees pre-selected breakout sessions on each theme they wanted to attend. During breakout sessions, attendees listened to selected speakers for each theme and asked questions of speakers. On the second day, after more keynote speakers, attendees participated in roundtable discussions on each theme and generated ideas and recommendations for all stakeholders to consider.

Across all speakers and themes, common ideas emerged about the complexity of increasing testing access in communities hardest hit by the COVID-19 pandemic. While the diversity of attendees was large – with some representing academic organizations, state, local, tribal and federal governments, community and faith organizations, foundations, healthcare systems, and industry — many common experiences and recommendations emerged.

First, attendees cited the need to provide testing in the places that make the most sense for those communities. While many testing interventions have relied on smartphone apps and drive-through locations, these interventions have missed many community members throughout the country who may not have easy access to the Internet, cell phone service, or cars. The solutions for different communities vary, but the problem is common: interventions too often take for granted that tools and resources that upper income people have are available to all. Messaging about COVID-19 testing faces a similar challenge and must be available in the right languages and forms of delivery, and from the right messengers, to truly reach the communities who need information.

Second, equity is needed in funding for COVID-19 testing and decision-making for community organizations partnering with academic and governmental researchers. Creating the tailored interventions and messages needed for unique communities requires experts only found within these communities. Whether it is linguistic support, knowledge of local media outlets, or even awareness of where people meet and whom they respect as trusted sources of information within a community, community partners and leaders are essential. They need to be considered experts in their community, funded appropriately, and part of planning and decision-making groups at every level of testing research and intervention.

Finally, while trustworthiness and equity served as its own cross-cutting theme, trust should be a fundamental element for any efforts related to COVID-19 testing and testing technologies. The issue of trust emerged in nearly every discussion throughout the event. Research can only move at the speed of trust. During the COVID-19 pandemic, when rapid decisions have been necessary, trust continues

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

to be tested, sometimes with unfavorable and even damaging consequences. While many long-standing partnerships are working to overcome disparities in testing, other partnerships have just started to collectively address the pandemic. However, disparate outcomes before the pandemic will persist unless partnerships are nurtured and sustained. Transparent communication throughout the research process, a commitment to fair and equitable partnerships with all relevant stakeholders, and extending efforts to overcome disparities after the pandemic, are all essential ingredients toward repairing and maintaining trust.

In this report, which is a companion to the **COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy 2021: TRANSLATING INNOVATIONS IN TESTING** data profile, you will find more information about attendees, the six-cross cutting themes of the event, a summary of keynote presentations, takeaway observations and recommendations from breakout sessions and roundtable discussions, illustrations from the event, and our lessons learned.

We are thankful to all who participated in this first Equity Evidence Academy and shared their experiences, their ideas, and their passion for repairing and strengthening our communities during and after the COVID-19 pandemic.

Purpose of the Evidence Academy

The COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy provides a starting place to jointly discuss these innovative ideas and make change in communities. An Evidence Academy is an engaged conference approach to understand the state-of-the-science, or the current evidence of COVID-19 testing and related factors in the populations most impacted. *The COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy 2021: Translating Innovations in Testing* was an invited inaugural event hosted by the Rapid Acceleration in Diagnostics-Underserved Population (RADx-UP) initiative in partnership with the Community Engagement Alliance (CEAL) Against COVID-19 Disparities initiative.

Attendee Demographics/ Characteristics

Attendee Overview—Attendance and Project Affiliation

Gathered from Scarritt registration data

NUMBER OF ATTENDEES

ATTENDEE PROJECT AFFILIATION

Attendee Overview—Race, Gender, and Ethnicity

Gathered from Scarritt registration data

GENDER

ETHNICITY

RACE

Note: 108 people did not report gender; 114 people did not report race; 121 people did not report ethnicity

Attendee Overview—Geography and Organizations

Gathered from Scarritt registration data

STATES REPRESENTED

Number of participants

- 0
- 1-15
- 16-30
- 31+

Note: 40/53 states and territories represented, including the District of Columbia (n=8), Puerto Rico (n=4), and the Virgin Islands (n=2)

REPORTED U.S. REGIONS

REPORTED URBANICITY/RURALITY

ORGANIZATIONS REPRESENTED

Summary of Keynote Presentations

DAY ONE

Day One included three keynote presentations to launch the Evidence Academy, and centered the attendees on the event's themes from a national perspective.

As part of the Evidence Academy, A Visual Approach, LLC created three comprehensive illustrations that reflected the live keynotes and breakout sessions, visually depicting the content being discussed.

ILLUSTRATED BY JACLYN GILSTRAP, A VISUAL APPROACH

FEBRUARY 24 - 25, 2021
COVID-19 EQUITY EVIDENCE ACADEMY

KEYNOTE ONE

Importance of COVID-19 Testing Technologies and Strategies

Eliseo J. Pérez-Stable, MD, Director, NIH/NIMHD

Dr. Eliseo J. Pérez-Stable, MD, the Director of the NIH's National Institute on Minority Health and Health Disparities (NIMHD) and first keynote speaker, discussed promoting health equity in the time of COVID-19.

Dr. Pérez-Stable first identified that social factors such as social determinants of health deepen social disadvantages and result in apparent health disparities, which are defined as “health outcomes that are worse in certain populations compared to a reference group.” As one of the authors on the article published in the Journal of American Medical Association, Dr. Pérez-Stable presented health disparity data specific to COVID-19 which showed > 50% of positive cases and 45% mortality occurring in certain racioethnic groups such as Latinos/LatinX, American Indians/Alaska Natives (AI/ANs), Pacific Hawaiian Islanders, and African Americans. The number of cases, hospitalizations, and deaths among these groups were about 1.6, 4, and 2.7 times as likely to occur when compared to non-Hispanic whites, respectively.

Because such data underscore the disproportionate burden of COVID-19 due to the long-standing disparities and disadvantages in groups of color, Dr. Pérez-Stable called for the use of standardized measurements to gather evidence on how exactly social determinants of health causes health disparities. He praised the important work of RADx-UP and CEAL around COVID-19 testing, research, and outreach while establishing trust in these populations and reaffirmed the commitment of NIH and NIMHD to addressing the structural racism as well as the social, behavioral, and economic impacts from COVID-19 through community engagement by “moving at the speed of trust.”

KEYNOTE TWO

Importance of Community in Addressing COVID-19 Testing

Yvette Roubideaux, MD, MPH, Director, Policy Research Center, NCAI

Dr. Yvette Roubideaux, MD, MPH, the Vice President for Research and the Director of the Policy Research Center at the National Congress of American Indians (NCAI), lauded the progress of the present-day willingness and participation in research among American Indian/ Alaska Native (AI/AN) tribal communities despite their grim history with research.

Outlining the initial challenges of the RADx-UP in its COVID-19 testing outreach with the tribal communities, Dr. Roubideaux encouraged researchers to first understand the vulnerability of these populations for testing and try to minimize harm. She then proceeded to pose this important question to the participants about building community-engaged research partnerships with this vulnerable population: “*Can research both protect and benefit a community?*”

Her advice was built on three pillars: **governance** (as a framework for ethical research and respect for tribal history), **trust** (a fragile but important building block based on honesty), and **culture** (by replacing any existing beliefs, perspectives, and assumptions with cultural humility). She reiterated that protecting and benefiting communities with COVID-19 testing are indeed possible by balancing research goals with community needs through meaningful partnerships.

KEYNOTE THREE

Implications of Today's Discussions for COVID-19 Testing in Aging Populations

Richard Hodes, MD, Director, NIH/NIA

Dr. Richard Hodes, MD, the Director of National Institute on Aging (NIA), opened his keynote presentation by describing the increased susceptibility of the elderly to COVID-19.

Citing the similarities between the elderly and minority populations and their increased risks for morbidity and mortality from COVID-19 infections, Dr. Hodes provided a complete overview of the six cross-cutting themes and presented research evidence around the elderly as possible tools to improve COVID-19 testing, research, and outreach in the minority populations. Namely, Dr. Hodes compared the similarities of the RADx-UP and CEAL initiatives to that of the NIH's Inclusion Across the Lifespan (IAL) in promoting the inclusion of under-represented groups such as the elderly and children in research and encouraged the lessons of IAL be applied to COVID-19 testing interventions in vulnerable populations for cultural and social considerations.

Acknowledging the socioeconomic barriers from social determinants of health and applicability of robust data science, Dr. Hodes emphasized the importance of building trust for equitable testing interventions and recommended culturally sensitive, targeted messaging to effectively reach the intended audience as communication challenges will uniquely vary among different communities.

Summary of Keynote Presentations

DAY TWO

BARRIERS

STRUCTURAL/OCCUPATIONAL

- Location of test facility
- messaging
- cost of test
- cost of care
- unable to take time off work
- no paid sick leave
- workman's comp concerns
- who pays?

BEHAVIORAL/QUALITY OF TEST

- False info
- Stigma
- Fear of discovery
- Lack of trust in "system"
- False positives
- Not confirmatory
- Availability
- Reliability

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR RESEARCH

"...must be the start of a relationship."

ENGAGE EARLY

BUILD TRUST

ASSURE CONFIDENTIALITY

ACCESS TO SERVICES

INFORM & EDUCATE

getvaccineanswers.org

IT'S UP TO YOU

“THE FIRST CONVERSATION YOU HAVE WITH A COMMUNITY OUGHT NOT TO BE ABOUT RESEARCH”

“You’ve gotta have TRUTH-TELLING & TRANSPARENCY before you can get to HEALING & RECONCILIATION”

~ DR. Patrice A. Harris
DAY 2 CLOSING KEYNOTE

the pandemic is highlighting LONGSTANDING HEALTH INEQUITIES for communities of color

COVID-19 & SOCIAL DETERMINANTS OF HEALTH

SAFETY AT WORK & PAID LEAVE

FOOD SECURITY

ACCESS TO TRANSPORTATION

CULTURE & LANGUAGE

INCOME & JOB SECURITY

SOCIAL ISOLATION

SAFE & AFFORDABLE HOUSING

ACCESS TO HEALTHCARE

CONTACT TRACING: LINKED STRATEGIES

TESTING: MUST ADDRESS TRUST ISSUES

“LISTEN FIRST”

“TWO EARS, ONE MOUTH”

WHAT IF WE LOOKED AT PUBLIC HEALTH ISSUES WITH intellectual honesty?

Thank You! HEALTHCARE WORKERS

GREAT LEADERS ARE NOT ABOUT THE TITLE, THEY ARE ABOUT THE WORK

IT'S OKAY TO NOT ALWAYS FEEL OKAY

Recognizing RACISM as an urgent THREAT to public HEALTH is essential to IMPROVING health outcomes

We call on our ELECTED OFFICIALS to affirm SCIENCE, EVIDENCE, & FACTS in their words & actions - no more JUNK SCIENCE

in times of crisis, we BUILD BRIDGES to knowledge and eliminate barriers

“SO WHILE WE ONCE ASKED ‘HOW COULD WE POSSIBLY PREVAIL OVER CATASTROPHE?’ NOW WE ASSERT, ‘HOW COULD CATASTROPHE POSSIBLY PREVAIL OVER US?’” ~ AMANDA GORMAN

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT is absolutely ESSENTIAL

engagement continuum

vaccine hesitancy? OR... Healthy skepticism? OR... Genuine curiosity? LET'S BE PREPARED EITHER WAY

~ DR. Georges C. Benjamin
DAY 2 OPENING KEYNOTE

NC-CEAL COMMUNITY RESPONSE TEAMS

BLACK/AFRICAN AMERICAN

AMERICAN INDIAN

HISPANIC/LATINX

COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy 2021: DAY 2

ILLUSTRATED BY JACLYN GILSTRAP, A VISUAL APPROACH

FEBRUARY 24 - 25, 2021
COVID-19 EQUITY EVIDENCE ACADEMY

KEYNOTE FOUR

Importance of Collectively Establishing Testing Plans of Action

Georges Benjamin, MD, Executive Director, APHA

Dr. Georges Benjamin, MD, the Executive Director of the American Public Health Association (APHA), emphasized community engagement as a continuum and how social determinants of health have contributed to COVID-19 disparities.

Citing the morbidity and mortality data presented by Dr. Pérez-Stable, Dr. Benjamin discussed how the lack of addressing social determinants of health contribute to minority groups' experience of health disparities including increased exposure and susceptibility to disease. He outlined four components under the umbrella of the social determinants of health that perpetuated testing inequities for COVID-19: structural barriers around access, behavioral barriers including misinformation and fear, occupational barriers such as inability to take time off from work, and the type and quality of tests available especially regarding the interpretation of “negative” results.

Dr. Benjamin explained equity issues with contact tracing and how social determinants of health have created challenges for tracing, social distancing, and following self-isolation/quarantine guidelines. Therefore, Dr. Benjamin strongly urged that testing and contact tracing be treated as linked rather than as separate actions.

He closed his presentation with five recommendations for building equitable community-based research partnerships: (1) **engage early** and throughout, (2) **build trust** by sharing frequent and accurate information through trusted messengers and trained professionals, (3) **provide access** to services for testing, contact tracing and isolation if necessary, (4) **assure confidentiality** of data and health information, and (5) **inform and educate** about health in culturally competent ways.

KEYNOTE FIVE

Moving the Science of COVID-19 Testing Forward Beyond the EA

Patrice Harris, MD, Past President, AMA

Dr. Patrice Harris, MD, the Immediate Past President of the American Medical Association (AMA), started and ended her keynote presentation with “pragmatically optimistic” messages on collective efforts based on science and facts to successfully combat the COVID-19 pandemic and applauded the RADx-UP and CEAL initiatives in promoting COVID-19 testing interventions in disproportionately impacted populations.

Dr. Harris recommended that attendants remember three things while facing health crises in America: intellectual honesty, discussions in context, and following science, evidence, and facts. Dr. Harris echoed Dr. Benjamin’s messages on the impact of social determinants of health as barriers to COVID-19 testing and outlined recommendations on how the resultant barriers could be overcome. Citing the recent efforts of the AMA on addressing racism and the disproportionate burden of COVID-19 among communities of color, Dr. Harris urged participants to center equity as the embedded DNA of community engagement and COVID-19 testing while remaining trustworthy. Dr. Harris referred to truth telling and transparency as prerequisites for healing and reconciliation and urged participants to “build bridges” to self, communities, science, evidence, and facts because “bridges will lead to solutions”.

In closing, Dr. Harris gave an encouraging remark by quoting the poem of Amanda Gorman, America’s Youth Poet Laureate, “How could catastrophe prevail over us?”

Definitions and Summaries of Six Cross-Cutting Themes

THEME 1

Cultural and Ethical Considerations

Cultural and ethnic factors that may influence testing. This may include such topics as: cultural, ethnic, linguistic, age and gender differences in testing behaviors by race and ethnicity (assets and challenges); community-centered approaches to testing; or cultural awareness around vaccines in under-resourced populations.

THEME 2

Social And Economic Costs

Social and/or economic barriers to testing. This may include such topics as: geographic and transportation access; language, insurance, and documentation issues; or large- and small-scale costs for testing resources.

THEME 3

Robust Data Science

Factors related to contact tracing and how a case is identified. This may include such topics as: linguistic considerations; resources and system logistics; and training and competencies necessary for quality contact tracing.

THEME 4

Trustworthiness and Equity

Factors, methods, and strategies related to communication and messaging on testing. These include such topics as: cultural awareness and risk communication; clarifying and understanding testing types; minimizing misinformation; creating common messages tailored to different communities' needs; trusted messengers; and sharing and implementing testing strategies.

THEME 5

Communication and Messaging

Trustworthy sources that can promote equity in testing. This may include such topics as: factors contributing to the fears of testing; institutional trustworthiness attributes when engaged in community-academic partnerships in testing and vaccinations; equity in testing and vaccinations; and methods for establishing trust through policy, research, and clinical practice.

THEME 6

Contact Tracing and Case Investigation

Conducting meaningful data science methods that address community context. This may include such topics as: shared data collection protocols (types of data and how they are shared and protected); risk assessments and surveillance; assessment of the impact of testing protocols on essential workers and community members; and contact tracing data collection and equity.

Summary of Session Themes

ILLUSTRATED BY JACQUELINE GUSTAFSON, A VISUAL APPROACH

FEBRUARY 24 - 25, 2021 COVID-19 EQUITY EVIDENCE ACADEMY

Insights and Recommendations from Session Themes

THEME 1

Cultural and Ethical Considerations

- Treat community partners equitably ensuring payment for services and non-hierarchical engagement by the research team. Use research as a mechanism for capacity building.
- Reduce requirements for common data elements. Establish community science advisory boards.
- Train additional people to conduct translation and interpretation to reduce the burden on bilingual staff and make sure that staff acting as translators and interpreters are trained on how to do this competently.
- Create a shared vision, address barriers to testing, and clarify what conditions need to exist to make things happen. This process is important in building trust.
- Trusted, culturally-proficient community stakeholders are important in developing and implementing successful COVID-19 testing strategies. Within the community, have people who serve as champions for COVID-19 testing and vaccination and engage people with diverse views to mitigate conspiracy theories.
- Build capacity, prioritize resources, and strengthen our national infrastructure to respond to public health demands.
- Decision-making must include diverse voices and attention to justice.
- Individual, public, and religious stances, as well as trust, influence cultural perspectives on testing and vaccination hesitancy. Stigmatization impacts testing behaviors.
- Historical trauma is the cumulative emotional and psychological wounding over lifetimes and across generations. It impacts a group's response to COVID-19 testing and vaccination. Four steps to recovery from historical trauma: 1) confronting; 2) understanding; 3) releasing; and 4) transcending the pain and trauma.
- We must take collective responsibility for addressing factors that influence access to health information. Factors include confidence, complacency, constraints, and calculations.

THEME 2 Social and Economic Costs

- Financial barriers might include lost wages from missing work and the cost of transportation to testing locations. Direct financial incentives as well as raising money for communities is recommended.
- Meet people where they live and work through mobile testing. Develop partnerships with trusted community leaders and identify sites that are convenient.
- Offer wraparound supports to support isolation while awaiting results and isolating or quarantining.
- Help build up local Community-Based Organizations' ability to partner with you by sharing resources such as training, technology, marketing, professional development, and data management.
- Increase support for community health worker programs, particularly ones that show effectiveness in reaching vulnerable community members.
- RADx-UP should collect and publish promising practices on reaching communities.
- Develop culturally-competent tools.
- The use of data and maps is essential in understanding social and economic costs of COVID-19 in diverse communities (for example, farmworkers in California).
- Service delivery planning to farmworkers will be improved by first ranking zip codes, then census tracts by levels of COVID risk.
 - In using available datasets to target outreach for testing, the most significant variables correlated with farmworkers by county should be used such as agricultural employment, high school diploma, poverty status, citizen status, language, etc.
 - Understanding social context and variables that contribute to higher risk in specific geographic areas allows for better planning for testing.
- If farmworkers are going to be reached with services, a huge investment in resources by government and philanthropies for outreach is necessary.
- There are obstacles in the law to addressing health inequities related to COVID-19:
 - Access to testing: Congress took steps to address those who are uninsured and those challenged by high co-pays, but loopholes and challenges persist.

INSIGHTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FROM SESSION THEMES

- Access to treatment: Congress took action for those most at risk and underserved, but did not focus on inequities among those with access to care.
- Immigrants with undocumented status: there are challenges in addressing barriers to testing and treatment without immigration system overhaul.
- Ability to quarantine: eviction moratorium and emergency rental assistance.
- Federal legislation has been enacted. However, efforts at local levels are needed.

THEME 3 Robust Data Science

- Be clear on the type of testing strategy and testing outcomes that are desired to determine means and methods.
- Compile testing protocols and testing technologies trade-offs.
- Integrate artificial intelligence into testing protocols.
- Ask “how do we integrate other data streams (for example, exposure reporting apps) into testing regimes?”
- Build a feedback loop to developers to highlight which type of testing is the best and most preferred by certain groups and consider the trade-offs of various assays.
- Conduct modelling of resource allocation and future demand.
- Find a quick but accurate test that can be used to meet underserved populations at their point of need.
- Screening tests can be used as part of an overall mitigation strategy (the “Swiss Cheese Model”).
- The free COVID-19 “When to Test” modeling tool can help leaders make informed decisions about their community environment, by assessing their existing mitigation measures and determine what types of testing is needed.
- “When To Test” Website – <https://whentotest.org/>
 - Allows user to input data on their mitigation measures, and outputs the costs and frequency of testing needed, given different test options.
 - It also allows the user to see how introducing other mitigation measures could reduce costs, or the need for screening testing altogether.

INSIGHTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FROM SESSION THEMES

- If high-risk settings routinely use screening testing, overall community coverage may be high, especially if combined with effective contact tracing.
- COVID-19 test performance can be determined by metrics, such as sensitivity (the extent a test is positive) and specificity (the extent a test is negative).
 - Highly sensitive tests are primarily used to diagnose COVID-19; highly specific tests are primarily used for screening for COVID-19.
- Types of specimens are critical in the testing approach selected.
 - For acute or active infection: nasopharyngeal swabs, saliva, shallow nasal swabs.
 - For previous infection: serum or plasma.
- Tests may perform differently for people with symptoms and those without.
- There are different types and levels of availability of at-home COVID-19 tests, varying by cost, prescription status, location for testing results (lab or at home), instructions, and authorization status.
- COVID-19 test performance can be determined by metrics, such as sensitivity (ability of test to correctly identify true positives) and specificity (ability of test to correctly identify true negatives).
 - Highly sensitive tests are primarily used to diagnose COVID-19; highly specific tests are primarily used for screening for COVID-19.
- Types of specimens are critical in the testing approach selected.
 - For acute or active infection: nasopharyngeal swabs, saliva, shallow nasal swabs
 - For previous infection: blood serum
- Tests may perform differently for people with symptoms and those without.
- There are different types and levels of availability of at-home COVID-19 tests, varying by cost, prescription status, location for testing results (lab or at home), instructions, and authorization status.

THEME 4

Trustworthiness and Equity

- Center the voices of those closest to the issue by creating space for decision making and in doing so, ensure the ability for collaborative and flexible processes for determining requirements (for example data collections, project goals, etc.).
 - There is a need to integrate trusted people from the community in information dissemination efforts. In addition to having them weigh in on topics, they should also be visible.
- Pathways are needed for individuals—particularly youth—to be more engaged. One example is community advisory boards, which can result in them getting more involved in the research and for them to learn more about research.
 - For example, creating curriculum to report findings; understand how funding works, and becoming PIs themselves in the future.
- Researchers or any outsiders going into a community need to be transparent about the limits of their expertise and what we know or do not know.
- Consider mandating a requirement for community dissemination in planning for funding.
- Work with communities prior to receiving the grant or funds. Ensure that resources such as hospitals are in place in those communities that would be necessary for reaching the goals of the project.
- Provide seed money to develop partnerships and build relationships where ideas can percolate out of the community.
- Build systems at the university level that mitigate and eliminate roadblocks to providing funds and that provide quick support to community members and do not request action from your community members or community organization until funds are secured and people can be paid.
- There are distinctions between the concepts of trust and trustworthiness.
 - Trust is a relationship developed between two individual moral agents, a trustor and trustee.
 - Trustworthiness is when a person or moral agent acknowledges the value of trust that is invested in the person by the trustor and uses that to decide how to act rightly.

INSIGHTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FROM SESSION THEMES

- Institutions conducting research should invest in structural competency, which requires a new approach to understanding relationships among race, class, and symptom expressions, and be mindful of the common humanity and dignity of persons we all share.
- Recognizing the dignity of persons and nurturing long-term relationships and collaborating to manage uncertainties are some of the lessons for trustworthiness.
- Communities can establish themselves as trusted partners. Steps to identifying a community trusted partner in engaged collaborations include attributes such as:
 - Knowledge of aligning systemic problems with the community organization's structure.
 - Record of leveraging captive audiences.
 - Financially stable, independent of the project.
- Research partnerships in COVID-19 involve developing shared community goals, such as asking who is “not at the table,” not ignoring existing structural inequities, and equity of power (“co” instead of “lead”).
- Trustworthiness and collaborative partnerships are necessary to implement COVID-19 testing protocols in populations greatly impacted.

THEME 5

Communication and Messaging

- Ask communities directly what sources they trust, and start there. Sustain community trust and engagement through trusted messengers. Note that trusted voices are necessary but not sufficient for effective communication. A “whole community” collaborative approach is necessary.
- Invest in multimodal communication (including 1:1 conversations) and media to bridge the digital divide. Engage with media outlets that are minority owned and operated. Messages need to be presented in several formats and platforms.
- Engage the community to co-create messages that incorporate relevant issues and barriers like immigration status concerns, or, Native American symbols. Communities should build their own messaging campaign using their own cultural experiences.
- NIH should help as a broker to connect with national chain store businesses that will be willing to help broader information dissemination in a community.

INSIGHTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FROM SESSION THEMES

- Understand the context behind risk perceptions before developing communication campaigns.
- Do not be afraid to engage in action and awareness.
- Engage in trauma-informed, culturally competent, honest, and mutually beneficial transactions with all stakeholders.
- Find ways to keep everyone engaged in the work over the long-term.
- Hold listening sessions over an extended period of time and conduct an environmental scan of community and organizational resources to set the tone for engagement. People listen better when they are heard.
- Data-driven communication strategies are needed.
- The key to authenticity is community dialogue that identifies and addresses real-world challenges.
- Vulnerable communities should have their own goals to push toward the future.
- Understand that communities and individuals within that community may identify themselves in ways that are different from the broader society.

THEME 6

Contact Tracing and Case Investigation

- Build relationships with individuals, households, and communities and facilitate education and collaborative listening sessions.
- Build capacity through partnerships among county public health departments and grassroots organizations.
- Integrate contact tracing at the point of testing.
- Integrate vaccination and testing education into overall efforts.
- Provide guidance to employers on testing.
- Personalize contact tracing and motivational interviewing for case investigation.
- Use of community health workers is one promising strategy to engage healthcare systems in light of COVID-19.
- Identify national LatinX community- and faith-based organizations to build capacity for greater reach and standards in communication.

INSIGHTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FROM SESSION THEMES

- Build in isolation/quarantine support and funding starting at Day 1.
- Build a statewide effort to support local health departments that includes identifying new or existing case investigation and contact tracing systems.
- Use race and ethnicity data to identify gaps to inform action plans.
- Prioritize the implementation of efficient processes to promote rapid and lasting buy-in.
- Develop early communication and messaging that instills trust necessary to increase efficiencies in service delivery, and appropriately manage contact tracing expectations.

Lessons Learned

The need for COVID-19 testing will remain for some time, even in the presence of vaccines. The six cross-cutting themes identified for this event applied to many health issues, not just COVID-19 testing. But by framing the event with these interconnected themes, attendees learned information from experts and from each other that can be readily applied to COVID-19 testing interventions, specifically to the conceptualization and planning phases as new, improved tests continue to be developed.

Over the course of the two-days, conversations centered on **the cross-cutting complexities and challenges of COVID-19 testing technologies**. All presentations reflected multiple and related themes, indicating the need for comprehensive or multi-dimensional solutions to COVID-19 testing. We learned that the state-of-the-science in COVID-19 testing not only includes a need for a basic understanding of the technology but also the social and environmental factors in communities who are most impacted by the disease.

We also learned that **population voices need to be elevated** as we work to collectively understand how to address the needs of diverse populations. This includes an increased focus in the future on American Indian, Native Alaska, Hawaiian Native and Asian populations, as well as continued emphasis on Black and Latinx populations.

This first national, virtual Evidence Academy can serve as a conference model for current information sharing and discussion, as it demonstrated its feasibility for engaging individuals with the RADx-UP and CEAL initiatives nationwide. **This event of 319 individuals was well-represented nationally** (38 states, the Virgin Islands, and the District of Columbia). This is vitally important, as community representation is necessary to understand the state-of-the-science and state-of-the-practice from diverse voices seeking to close the gap in translation in testing and testing technologies.

We hope that the social connections made during this event will serve as a useful springboard for collaboration, not only within RADx-UP and CEAL projects, but also between RADx-UP and CEAL networks. Scaling up evidence-based approaches through collaborative discussions may help to **more rapidly advance the science, build needed trust, and create more equitable opportunities for health** beyond the pandemic.

Appendix: Acknowledgments

LEADERSHIP OF THE RADx-UP CDCC AND CEAL I-TEAM

RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC) Co-Principal Investigators

Micky Cohen-Wolkowicz, MD, PhD
Duke Clinical Research Institute

Giselle Corbie-Smith, MD, MSc
University of North Carolina (UNC)
Center for Health Equity Research

Warren Kibbe, PhD
Duke University

CEAL I-TEAM Co-Principal Investigators

Anissa Vines, PhD
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Al Richmond, MSW
Community-Campus Partnerships for Health

Goldie Byrd, PhD
Wake Forest University and the Maya Angelou Center for Health Equity

STEERING COMMITTEE MEMBERS

Sergio Aguilar-Gaxiola, MD, PhD
University of California, Davis

Natalie Bowman, MD
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Arleen Brown, MD, PhD
University of California, Los Angeles

Dedra Buchwald, MD
Washington State University

Edward Kissam
The Werner-Kohnstamm Family Giving Fund (WKF)

Jay Leggette
The Stimulus

Erica Marsh, MD, MSCI, FACOG
University of Michigan

Viviana Martinez-Bianchi, MD, FAAFP
Duke University

Marcella Nunez-Smith, MD, MHS
Yale School of Medicine

William Owen, MD, FACP
Ross University School of Medicine

Donald Warne, MD, MPH
University of North Dakota

Christopher Woods, MD, PhD
Duke University

REPORT DEVELOPERS

Lori Carter-Edwards, PhD, MPH
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Jeannie Hong, PharmD, BCPS
Phoenix Indian Medical Center

Heather Wilson
Duke Clinical Research Institute

Zhitong Yu
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Prabisha Shrestha
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Bukola Adeshina, MPH
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Alicia Bilheimer, MPH
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Renee Leverty, MA
Duke Clinical Research Institute

Jenny Cook, MPH
Duke Clinical Research Institute

A Visual Approach, LLC
Live session illustrations

Complex Stories, Design and Layout

CORE PLANNING TEAM

Lori Carter-Edwards, PhD, MPH
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Renee Leverty, MA
Duke Clinical Research Institute

Bukola Adeshina, MPH
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Alicia Bilheimer, MPH
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

APPENDIX: ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

FULL PLANNING TEAM

Deepti Baheti, MD

United Medical Center (TX)

Kathleen (Katie) Brandert, MPH, CHES

University of Nebraska

Shelley Brunson

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Ann Burnette

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Crystal Cannon, MA

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Elizabeth Chege, MA

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Simone Claire Frank, MPH

North Carolina TraCS Institute

Rosa Gonzalez-Guarda, PhD, MPH

Duke University Clinical Translational Science Institute

Barrie Harper

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Laura Johnson, MHS

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Susan Knox

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Krista Perreira, PhD

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Hannah Marie Potter, MPH

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Rachel Quinto

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Al Richmond, MSW

Community-Campus Partnerships for Health

Christina Silcox, PhD

Duke-Margolis Center for Health Policy

Andrea Thoumi, MPP, MSc

Duke-Margolis Center for Health Policy

Miranda Wenhold, MSEd

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

FUNDERS AND SPONSORS PLANNING TEAM

The RADx-UP CDCC, which is funded through an NIH emergency cooperative agreement, 1U24MD016258

The NC CEAL, I-TEAM, which is funded through a NIH-NHLBI sponsored award, 17-312-0217571-66099L

SCHOOL OF MEDICINE
North Carolina
Translational and
Clinical Sciences
Institute

North Carolina Translational and Clinical Sciences (NC TraCS) Institute, the home of the UNC Clinical and Translational Science Awards (CTSA), grant number UL1TR002489

PROJECT OFFICERS AND PROJECT SCIENTISTS OF THE NIH-FUNDED RADx-UP AND CEAL INITIATIVES

National Institute on Minority Health and Health Disparities—

Monica Hooper, PhD, Nathaniel Stinson, MD, MPH, PhD, Dorothy Castille, PhD, Beda Jean-Francois, PhD, Maryline Laude-Sharp, PhD, Nadra Tyus, DrPH, MPH, Fabienne Santel, MD

National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute—George Mensa, MD, Catherine Stoney, PhD

National Institute on Aging—Partha Bhattacharyya, PhD

Appendix: Agenda

COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy 2021: Translating Innovations in Testing AGENDA

DAY 1 (12:00 – 5:00PM EST, February 24, 2021)

12:00-12:05	Welcome, Overview of the Annual EA Series – Micky Cohen-Wolkowicz, MD, PhD; MPI, RADx-UP CDCC (Duke)		
12:05-12:15	Attendee-to-Attendee Greetings, Small Group Opportunity for participants to get voices in the room and engage in the meeting. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greetings and brief intros • What is one thing you hope to gain by participating in this Equity Evidence Academy? 		
12:15-12:25	Land Acknowledgment, Introduction of 1st Keynote – Giselle Corbie-Smith, MD, MSc; MPI, RADx-UP CDCC (UNC)		
12:25-12:50	DAY 1 OPENING KEYNOTE ADDRESS: IMPORTANCE OF COVID-19 TESTING TECHNOLOGIES AND STRATEGIES <i>Eliseo J. Pérez-Stable, MD; Director, National Institute on Minority Health and Health Disparities (NIMHD) - NIH</i>		
12:50-12:55	Introduction of 2nd Keynote – Al Richmond, MSW; MPI, CEAL I-TEAM; Co-Lead, Community and Health Systems Engagement Core, RADx-UP CDCC (CCPH)		
12:55-1:20	DAY 1 COMMUNITY KEYNOTE ADDRESS: IMPORTANCE OF COMMUNITY IN ADDRESSING COVID-19 TESTING <i>Yvette Roubideaux, MD, MPH; Director of the Policy Research Center, National Congress of American Indians (NCAI)</i>		
1:20-1:30	Overview of Equity EA: Testing Innovations – Lori Carter-Edwards, PhD, MPH; EA Lead (UNC) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purpose and Objectives of the First National EA’s Focus on Testing Innovations • Review of the Day’s Activities 		
1:30-1:35	Break		
1:35-2:25	CONCURRENT BREAKOUT SESSION I (per session: 30 minutes for presentation; 20 minutes for discussion)		
	Theme 1: Cultural and Ethical Considerations <i>(Reporter: Catherine Rohweder)</i>	Theme 2: Social and Economic Costs <i>(Reporter: Simone Frank)</i>	Theme 3: Robust Data Science <i>(Reporter: Christina Silcox)</i>
	Session 1a: Understanding and Alleviating Fears in COVID-19 Testing <i>Speaker: Allan Chrisman, MD</i> Facilitator: Crystal Cannon Scribe: Claire Beard Chat Monitor: Ann Burnette	Session 2a: Barriers to and Effective Strategies for Improving COVID-19 Service Delivery to Farmworkers <i>Speaker: Rick Mines, PhD, MA</i> Facilitator: Rosa Gonzalez-Guarda Scribe: Deepti Ramesh Baheti Chat Monitor: David Anderson	Session 3a: Assessment of Testing Protocols Utilizing Community Context <i>Speakers: Paul Tessier, BS; Sarah Fay, PhD Candidate</i> Facilitator: Courtney Mann Scribe: Prabisha Shrestha Chat Monitor: Laura Johnson
	Session 1b: Building Cultural and Linguistic Capacity in COVID-19 Testing <i>Speakers: Felix Valbuena, MD; Cherry Maynor Beasley, PhD, MS, FNP</i> Facilitator: Jenny Cook Scribe: Zhitong Yu Chat Monitor: Hannah Potter	Session 2b: Social Justice and COVID-19 Testing Research <i>Speaker: Audrey Anderson, JD</i> Facilitator: Anton Zuiker Scribe: Nisha Datta Chat Monitor: Stephanie Baker	Session 3b: Bi-Directional Translation of COVID-19 Testing Protocols <i>Speakers: Eric Perakslis, PhD; Tom Denny, Msc, M.Phil</i> Facilitator: Donna Parker Scribe: Laura Ann Johansen Chat Monitor: Barrie Harper
2:25-2:35	Break		

APPENDIX: AGENDA

COVID-19 EQUITY EVIDENCE ACADEMY 2021

2:35-3:25		CONCURRENT BREAKOUT SESSION II (per session: 30 minutes for presentation; 20 minutes for discussion)		
Theme 4: Trustworthiness and Equity (Reporter: Mary Beth Grewe)		Theme 5: Communication and Messaging (Reporter: Laura Villa Torres)	Theme 6: Contact Tracing and Case Investigation (Reporter: Andrea Thoumi)	
Session 4a: Establishing Trustworthiness when Conducting Research on COVID-19 Testing <i>Speaker: Stephen Sodeke, PhD, MA</i> Facilitator: Courtney Mann Scribe: Claire Beard Chat Monitor: Ann Burnette		Session 5a: Core Principles in Health Risk Communication in COVID-19 Testing <i>Speakers: Amanda Boyd, PhD; Rodney Washington, EdD, MS</i> Facilitator: Jenny Cook Scribe: Deepti Ramesh Baheti Chat Monitor: David Anderson	Session 6a: The Role of Public Health Departments in Contact Tracing <i>Speakers: Linda Ivory-Green, MS, CSW; Victoria Mobley, MD, MPH</i> Facilitator: Donna Parker Scribe: Prabisha Shrestha Chat Monitor: Laura Johnson	
Session 4b: Activating Principles of Engagement to Build Trustworthiness for COVID-19 Testing Efforts <i>Speakers: James D. Gailliard, MBA, MDiv; Gerardo Reyes Chavez</i> Facilitator: Crystal Cannon Scribe: Zhitong Yu Chat Monitor: Hannah Potter		Session 5b: Communication and Grassroots Advocacy in COVID-19 Testing <i>Speakers: Ed Kissam, PPE; Jay Leggette</i> Facilitator: Anton Zuiker Scribe: Nisha Datta Chat Monitor: Stephanie Baker	Session 6b: Mobilizing Collaboration and Contact Tracing Advocacy in LatinX Communities <i>Speaker: Norma Martí, BA</i> Facilitator: Rosa Gonzalez-Guarda Scribe: Laura Ann Johansen Chat Monitor: Barrie Harper	
3:25-3:35		Break		
3:35-4:00		Reporters Summarize the Six Breakout Sessions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Highlights from the presentations and discussions 		
4:00-4:05		Introduction of Closing Keynote – Warren Kibbe, PhD; MPI, RADx-UP CDCC (Duke)		
4:05-4:30		DAY 1 CLOSING KEYNOTE ADDRESS: IMPLICATIONS OF TODAY’S DISCUSSIONS FOR COVID-19 TESTING IN AGING POPULATIONS <i>Richard Hodes, MD; Director, National Institute on Aging (NIA) - NIH</i>		
4:30-4:50		Attendee-to-Attendee Closure, Small Group Opportunity for participants to connect and bring closure to the day. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Greetings and brief intros What is one significant takeaway for you from the day? 		
4:50-5:00		Closing Remarks and Instructions for Day 2 – Giselle Corbie-Smith, MD, MSc; MPI, RADx-UP CDCC (UNC)		

DAY 2 (12:00 – 3:00PM EST, February 25, 2021)

12:00-12:05	Welcome, Purpose of the Day’s Activities – Anissa Vines, PhD; MPI, CEAL I-TEAM (UNC)
12:05-12:15	Attendee-to-Attendee Greetings, Small Group Opportunity for participants to connect and engage on expectations for next steps based on Day 1. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Greetings and brief intros What is one word you would use to describe your experience with the Evidence Academy so far?
12:15-12:20	Introduction of Opening Keynote – Krista Perreira, PhD; Co-Lead, Community and Health Systems Engagement Core, RADx-UP CDCC; Co-Lead, Hispanic/Latinx Community Response Team, CEAL I-TEAM (UNC)
12:20-12:45	DAY 2 OPENING KEYNOTE ADDRESS: IMPORTANCE OF COLLECTIVELY ESTABLISHING TESTING PLANS OF ACTION <i>Georges C. Benjamin, MD; Director, American Public Health Association (APHA)</i>

APPENDIX: AGENDA

COVID-19 EQUITY EVIDENCE ACADEMY 2021

12:45-12:50	Instructions for Roundtable Discussions – Katie Brandert, MPH; Facilitator, Consultant, RADx-UP CDCC		
12:50-1:30	ROUNDTABLE DISCUSSIONS		
	Theme 1: Cultural and Ethical Considerations <i>(Reporter: Catherine Rohweder)</i>	Theme 2: Social and Economic Costs <i>(Reporter: Christina Silcox)</i>	Theme 3: Robust Data Science <i>(Reporter: Jeannie Hong)</i>
	Facilitator Room 1: Donna Parker Facilitator Room 2: Brandy Farrar Facilitator Room 3: Michael Muhammad Facilitator Room 4: Anton Zuiker	Facilitator Room 1: Kevin Van Dyke Facilitator Room 2: Monica Richard Facilitator Room 3: Ken Wolf Facilitator Room 4: Susan Knox	Facilitator Room 1: Courtney Mann Facilitator Room 2: Simone Frank Facilitator Room 3: Ann Marie Akiwumi Facilitator Room 4: David Anderson
	Theme 4: Trustworthiness and Equity <i>(Reporter: Katie Brandert)</i>	Theme 5: Communication and Messaging <i>(Reporter: Laura Villa Torres)</i>	Theme 6: Contact Tracing and Case Investigation <i>(Reporter: Andrea Thoumi)</i>
	Facilitator Room 1: Hannah Potter Facilitator Room 2: Crystal Cannon Facilitator Room 3: MaryBeth Grewe Facilitator Room 4: Maryland Grier-Union	Facilitator Room 1: Jenny Cook Facilitator Room 2: Heather Wilson Facilitator Room 3: Nisha Datta Facilitator Room 4: Julia Rehder	Facilitator Room 1: Rosa Gonzalez- Guarda Facilitator Room 2: Alberto Ortega-Hinojosa Facilitator Room 3: Ekiuwa Imariagbe Facilitator Room 4: Miranda Wenhold
1:30-1:40	Break		
1:40-2:10	Reporters Summarize the Roundtable Discussions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Highlights of the recommended action plans. 		
2:10-2:15	Introduction of Closing Keynote – Goldie Byrd, PhD; MPI, CEAL I-TEAM (Wake Forest)		
2:15-2:40	DAY 2 CLOSING KEYNOTE ADDRESS: MOVING THE SCIENCE OF COVID-19 TESTING FORWARD BEYOND THE EVIDENCE ACADEMY <i>Patrice Harris, MD, MA; Past President, American Medical Association (AMA)</i>		
2:40-2:55	Attendee-to-Attendee Closure, Small Group Opportunity for participants to connect and bring closure to the EA. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Greetings and brief intros What is one action you will take as a result of the day’s roundtable discussions? 		
2:55-3:00	Closing Remarks – Lori Carter-Edwards, PhD, MPH; EA Lead (UNC)		

Acronyms:

- EA:** Evidence Academy
- MPI:** Multiple Principal Investigator
- RADx-UP:** Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics – Underserved Populations
- CDCC:** Coordination and Data Collection Center
- UNC:** University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
- CEAL:** Community Engagement Alliance Against COVID-19 Disparities
- I-TEAM:** Increasing Trustworthiness through Engaged Action and Mobilization
- CCPH:** Community-Campus Partnerships for Health

Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics-Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) is an initiative of the The National Institutes of Health, in partnership with the Duke Clinical Research Institute and the UNC Center for Health Equity Research. RADx-UP aims to ensure that all Americans have access to COVID-19 testing, with a focus on communities across the country that most affected by the pandemic. The initiative is researching testing patterns, disparities in infection rates, disease progression and outcomes in those communities. It is also developing strategies to reduce disparities in COVID-19 testing by supporting projects across the country with established community partnerships.

For more information visit RADx-UP.org

The RADx-UP CDCC is funded through an NIH emergency cooperative agreement 1U24MD016258

